

Digital Preservation and Data Retention for Research Data

Preservation considerations for research data can begin as early as the planning phase of the research project. The preservation considerations at the planning phase can be supplied to a repository to help the repository determine preservation activities for your dataset.

Does the data have long term value?

Consider how the data can be reused in the future by you and by others.

- Does the data need to be used for verification purposes?
- Will the data be used for future research and analysis?
- Does the data communicate and contribute to current and emerging knowledge and perspectives in your field?
- Will the data be used for learning and teaching?
- How valuable is the data in communicating current knowledge and perspectives?
- Does the data demonstrate potential ongoing social, scientific or historical value?

Does the data need to be kept for funder or policy compliance?

Consider any legislation, policy or funding requirements that may dictate what data needs to be kept and potentially for how long.

- Does any legislation apply to your data?
- Is the data used in a patent application?
- Do agreements state or imply that data must be retained?
- Are there disciplinary regulations that require data to be kept?

What data should be kept?

Consider if all the data generated need to be kept or only part of it.

- Are the collection methods, processing methods, and the nature of the data documented?
- Is the data unique (there is only one complete copy of the data)?
- Is the data expected to be kept by the community?
- Do people, (funders, research groups, colleagues), expect this data will remain available for a long time?
- Will the data be superseded or available in another form?

Adapted from Robyn Stobbs, "Understanding Data Deposit," 2025-02-13 and Digital Curation Centre, "Five steps to decide what data to keep: DCC Checklist for Appraising Research Data, 2014"